

**CONTRIBUTION ON SUPERVISION OF SUPERVISOR,
PRINCIPALS MOTIVATION, KINDERGARTEN TEACHER
PERFORMANCE TO IMPROVING THE KINDERGARTEN QUALITY
IN WEST BANJARMASIN, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

This study aims to find out: Direct contributions 1) Supervision of the supervisor on the Kindergarten Principal's Motivation; 2) Principal's Motivation towards Teacher's performance; 3) Supervision of Supervisors on Teacher's performance; 4) Principal's Motivation towards quality; 5) Supervision of the supervisor on quality; 6) Teacher's performance on quality. Indirect contributions: 7) Principal's Motivation through intermediaries Teacher performance on quality; 8) Supervision of Supervisors through intermediaries Teacher performance on quality; 9) Supervision of the supervisor through intermediary of Principal's Motivation on quality; 10) Supervision through Principal's Motivation and Teachers Performance on quality. The primary data obtained and tested were hypothesized from a population of 64 Kindergartens using total population sampling technique and from 238 teachers using proportional random sampling technique using the Solvin formula in West Banjarmasin District with an error rate of 5%, obtained 139 Kindergarten teachers as samples. Data collection techniques through library research, field research, observation and questionnaire. The method used is descriptive. Research instruments using questionnaires and observations. Data Analysis used to test hypotheses using Path Analysis. Data is analyzed by paths built based on the research paradigm. The results of study showed that there are direct contributions to: 1) supervision of the supervisor to kindergarten principal's motivation; 2) principal's motivation towards teacher's performance; 3) supervision of supervisors on teacher's performance; 4) principal's motivation towards quality 5) supervision of the supervisor on quality; 6) teacher's performance on quality. Some other showed indirect contributions to: 7) principal's motivation through intermediaries teacher performance on quality. 8) supervision of the supervisor through intermediaries teacher

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performance on quality. The results of study also showed there are no direct contributions to: 9) supervision of the supervisor through intermediary of principal's motivation on quality; and 10) supervision of supervisors and quality through intermediaries of principal's motivation and teachers' performance in kindergarten Sub District of West Banjarmasin.

Keywords: supervision of supervisors, principals' motivation, teacher performance, quality of kindergarten

1. Introduction

In order for Indonesia to become a competitive and respectable large country in the eyes of the world, it requires the support and commitment of all parties to carry out early childhood education (PAUD) education. PAUD is an education to develop a variety of potential children from an early age as a preparation to face life so that it can adapt to its environment before entering the world of higher education. Educational staff must be patient and diligent in educating according to the potential, interests, talents and abilities of early childhood. It is the right time to lay the foundations for developing physical, language, social, moral, emotional, religious, character and independence concepts so that children's growth and development can be achieved optimally.

Education in schools acts as a means of realizing one of the goals of a country, namely to educate the life of the nation and to develop Indonesian people as a whole. Schools have a complex and unique nature so schools as organizations need a high level of coordination. The role of supervisors in providing supervision of guidance and developing professional competence to principals and teachers is very significant towards productivity and effectiveness. The role of the school principal as a motivator, namely how the principal improves teacher performance through the motivation given. According to Suriansyah et al. (2014), in the learning process, the teacher does not only act as a model or role model for the students he teaches, but also as a manager of learning. Thus, the effectiveness of the learning process lies on the shoulders of the teacher. Therefore, the success of a learning process is largely determined by the quality or ability of the teacher.

According to Sutisna (1982), the role of supervisor is as a supervisor who aims to improve learning and teaching, in addition to guiding the growth of teachers' professional abilities and skills. More specifically to encourage teachers to become more empowered, and learning situations to be better and more effective, teachers become more satisfied in carrying out their duties so that the results of supervision carried out by Supervisors on teachers have a major influence on improving teacher performance. The role of supervisor as a supervisor is to motivate, control/monitor, evaluate and assess the principal (managerially) and the teacher (academically) in the implementation of education at a quality PAUD level. The involvement of school

principals and supervisors in improving the quality of education is a measure of the success of the main tasks and functions of supervisors and principals. Teachers are the main key in educating students, with high teacher performance can increase student achievement. A school as an organizational institution to make quality schools needed the role of a leader who is able and willing to change the condition of the school towards improvement. Schools are no longer managed by routine methods but how do the principals' ability to carry out the most important tasks can manage quality educational institutions. Quality is not only meant to meet needs but also related to predetermined standards (Metroyadi, 2015). In relation to schools, the quality problem becomes one of the relevant issues to be discussed. In this case the role is students, parents, and other interested parties, where parents are often not satisfied with the services provided by the school. This often happens because in terms of service a school is still below the standard of quality service. In schools, there is often a lack of efficient use of resources and counterproductive activities which result in not achieving the objectives of national education. The large number of schools with different levels of quality in Indonesia needs government support to break the quality of education. While the general problem that is often faced by the government in the development of national education is a quality problem. The quality of education can be improved through a variety of ways, including "quality control". Currently efforts to improve the quality of education nationally are one of the programs being implemented by the government in collaboration with all stakeholders involved in school education. To be able to compare and assess the quality of each education unit, accreditation is needed for every educational institution in Indonesia. The accreditation process is carried out periodically and openly with comprehensive and developed instruments based on quality standards set nationally by NAA (National Accreditation Agency).

Considering that there is a number of obstacles to the extent of Indonesia's state in the implementation of accreditation, the accreditation implementation costs are quite large, where the costs must be borne by each school that applies for accreditation and many schools in remote areas that are not ready with the accreditation requirements. Therefore, not all kindergarten schools in West Banjarmasin District can do accreditation. To find out the quality of kindergarten schools in West Banjarmasin, the authors are interested in doing research on quality in another way, namely collecting data and looking for relationships from a number of research variables that exist through descriptive research, which is trying to describe existing variables and also intended to predict the closeness of variable relationships. One against another variable between predictor and one variable criteria (Sugiyono, 2015). This study uses four variables identified in three categories: Supervision of the supervisor variable and Principal's Motivation variable as an independent variable (independent variable) and kindergarten teacher performance as an intervening variable and the quality of Kindergarten as dependent variable. Regression technique is research that characterizes contributions that are between two or more variables (Arikunto, 2004).

This study aims to find out direct contributions of: 1) supervision of the supervisor on the kindergarten principal's motivation; 2) principal's motivation towards teacher's performance; 3) supervision of supervisors on teacher's performance; 4) principal's motivation towards quality; 5) supervision of the supervisor on quality; and 6) teacher's performance on quality. There some indirect contributions such as: 7) principal's motivation through intermediaries teacher performance on quality; 8) supervision of supervisors through intermediaries teacher performance on quality; 9) supervision of the supervisor through intermediary of principal's motivation on quality; and 10) supervision through principal's motivation and teachers performance on quality.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Quality of Kindergarten

Understanding quality implies the meaning of the degree of excellence of a product/work, can be in the form of goods or services; either tangible or intangible. According to Shomad (2014), the quality of education is a multidimensional concept covering institutionalization, teaching and student learning outcomes. Higher quality education in Indonesia is expected by educators, educational institutions and the government. According to Wirakartakusumah (Rajagukguk, 2009) in order to achieve quality education, a new paradigm in education is needed that focuses on accountability, autonomy, accreditation and evaluation. The four pillars of management are expected to create quality education in the end. The quality of education can be measured by indicators which include: Competencies of Graduates, Content, Processes, Educators and Education Personnel, Facilities and Infrastructure, Management, Financing and Assessment of Education.

2.2 Supervision of Kindergarten Supervisors

School supervision has often been heard, but it is not necessarily comprehensible comprehensively, in the words of the word, supervision comes from the English Supervision term. Supervision consists of two words Super (more) and Vision (seeing) (Arikunto, 2004). According to Suhardan (2010), a supervisor is a professional when carrying out his duties, and he acts on the basis of scientific principles to improve the quality of education. To carry out these basic tasks, the school supervisor carries out the supervision function, namely: a) Academic supervision is a supervision function that deals with the aspects of coaching and developing the professional ability of teachers in improving the quality of learning and guidance in schools; b) Managerial supervision is a supervision function that deals with aspects of school management that are directly related to improving school efficiency and effectiveness. The indicators used in Supervisor Supervision variables in this study are Planning, Implementation, Socialization and Improvement.

2.3 Principal's Motivation of Kindergarten

The task of the Principal is one component of education that has an important role in improving the quality of education. The complexity of the task demands of school principals who want more effective and efficient performance support. According to Suriansyah (2015), principals' leadership behaviors can not only be understood from general behavior, such as "vision" and "mission" only, but also must be identified in specific (specific) actions that are innovative and creative activities of the principal in carry out his leadership and daily school management. Motivation will be born if the leader realizes that his function is capable of being a motivator. According to Hamalik (2003) there are 3 motivational functions, namely: a) encouraging a change; b) as the director of actions to achieve the desired goals; and c) as a driver means to function like a machine in a car. There are several motivational theories such as Maslow's theory that hierarchy of needs can actually be used to detect human motivation. Herzberg's theory said ideal motivation is an opportunity to carry out tasks that require more expertise or an opportunity to develop abilities. There are two factors that influence a person's work productivity, that is maintenance factors and motivating factors. David McClland's theory, explains that everyone has a need that encourages the achievement of the will that is the drive to work for achievement. Therefore, the role of the principal as a motivator is very important for improving teacher performance. Douglas Mc Gregor's Theory is a theory of motivation known as the theory of X and the theory of Y. The theory of X manager views the workers as irreparable repellents. Theory Y views that people basically tend to work hard and do good work. Indicators of work motivation in this study are the Heads of Kindergarten who provide directives and orders to motivate the performance of Kindergarten Teachers through a strong Personality, Understanding the purpose of education well, Strong basic knowledge, Strong professional competence, Skills conceptional.

2.4 Performance of Kindergarten Teachers

According to Mangkunegara (2009) performance is the result of work in the quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. The definition of performance is a result of work produced by an employee who is directed to achieve the expected goals. According to Sanusi (2011) and the concept of teacher performance article 8, UUGD number 14/2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers states that teacher performance is a professional level of teachers in the teaching and learning process during a certain period which is revealed in mastering four components, namely: (a) pedagogic, (b) personality; (c) social; and (d) professionals. Some aspects that will be used as indicators in teacher performance variables in this study are: pedagogic, personality, social and professional.

3. Methods

This type of research will be conducted using a quantitative approach. The design of this quantitative research uses descriptive method and correlational design using statistical analysis techniques called Path Analysis. The population in this study was all kindergartens in West Banjarmasin sub-district according to National Education sub-district of West Banjarmasin in the 2017/2018 school year totaling 64 kindergartens or 64 principals and 238 kindergarten teachers. The sampling technique for schools used in this study uses total population sampling, where in this study using all subjects as a sample and for the kindergartens headmaster and teacher using proportional random sampling with the Slovin formula 5% error rate. The data collection was used by Library Research and Field Research techniques through interviews, questionnaires, observations and a combination of the three with a questionnaire or questionnaire distribution method. In this study, the existing questionnaire contained the questions used to reveal the supervisory supervisor's variables, the principal's motivation and the teacher's performance as well as the quality of Kindergarten filled directly by the respondents. The questionnaire that was filled entirely was a closed questionnaire model of the Likert Scale. Formulation of questions in the questionnaire is based on the indicators of the research variables, both independent variables, dependent variables and intervening variable.

Using the construct validity test and content validity test with the Product-Moment Correlation formula and the Corrected Item-Total Correlation Technique with the IBM SPSS 20 program. Validity test results instrument showed managerial supervisor supervision by $r_{count} > r_{table}$ ($0.05 > 0.361$), then all items about 16 items said valid and will be used entirely in this study. Supervision of kindergartens supervisors tested validity test shows valid results. The performance instruments produced 19 items of headmaster and 18 items of teacher were valid. Quality of kindergarten there are 50 valid items. In this study, the reliability test of each variable was measured using Cronbach's alpha. According to Eisingerich and Rubera (2010), the value of the minimum Cronbach's Alpha reliability level is 0.70. Besides being seen based on Cronbach's Alpha, a reliable indicator can also be seen from the value of correlated item-total correlation. Correlated item-total correlation can also be used to delete indicators that are not reliable in a variable. The value of correlated item-total correlation in an indicator to be declared reliable is a minimum of 0.50 (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 1: Reliability Test Results Instrument Managerial Supervision Supervisors, Academic Supervisor Supervision, Principal's Motivation, and Teacher Performance and Quality of Kindergarten

Variable	Item		Cronbach's Alpha Value
	Valid	Not Valid	
Managerial Supervision Supervisors	16	0	0,968
Academic Supervisor Supervision	16	0	0,968
Principal's Motivation	19	1	0,949
Teacher Performance	18	2	0,912
Quality of Kindergarten	50	1	0,978

The results of the analysis used with the help of the IBM SPSS 20 program obtained the Alpha value on the managerial supervisor Supervision instrument of 0.968, Academic 0.968, Principal's Motivation 0.949, Teacher performance 0.912 and quality of Kindergarten 0.978, all > the minimum value of Cronbach's Alpha 0.70, so all the research instruments are very reliable.

Data analytical techniques with Path Analysis are shown in the following figure:

Figure 1: Model of Three Independent/Independent Variable Paths

This analysis will be used in testing the magnitude of the contribution shown by the correlation coefficient between variables: Supervision of Supervisor (X1) on principal's motivation (X2), Principal's motivation (X2) on the performance of Teacher (Y), Supervisor Supervision (X1) on Teacher performance (Y), Principal's motivation (X2) directly to quality (Z), Supervision of Supervisor (X1) directly to quality (Z), Teacher Performance (Y) to quality (Z), Principal's Motivation (X2) through intermediaries Teacher Performance (Y) towards quality (Z), Supervision of Supervisor (X1) through intermediary Teacher Performance (Y) to quality (Z), Supervision of Supervisor (X1) through intermediaries Principal's motivation (X2) towards quality (Z), Supervisory Supervision (X1) through intermediaries principal's motivation (X2) and through Teacher Performance (Y) on quality (Z).

Based on Figure 1, a pathway model for each structure is then developed. Path analysis is used to determine the relationship of independent variables with the dependent variable through the intermediary of the other independent variables used by the mathematical equation for the selection of structures, namely:

Pathway Model Structure I

The first phase is identified, which consists of 1 independent variable, Supervisor Supervision (X1), to Principal's Motivation of the dependent variable (X2).

Pathway Model Structure II

Then the second stage examined two independent variables, namely Supervision of Supervisors (X1) and Principal's Motivation (X2) and 1 dependent variable namely Teacher Performance (Y)

Pathway Model Structure III

Furthermore, the third stage examined three independent variables, namely Supervision of supervisors (X1) and Principal's motivation (X2) and Teacher Performance (Y) on quality of Kindergarten (Z) as dependent variables.

The mathematical equation is as follows:

The first structural equation : $X_2 = \beta_1 X_1 + e_1$

The second structural equation : $Y = \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_1 + e_2$

The third structural equation : $Z = \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_5 Y + \beta_3 X_1 + e_3$

4. Results and Discussion

Path analysis is used to explain the phenomenon under study, predict the value of Quality endogenous variable (Z) based on the exogenous variable value Supervisory Supervision (X1), Motivation variable (X2) and Teacher Performance (Y) trace the mechanism (pathways) the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variable.

Based on the results of the multiple regression test, the first structural equation $X_2 = \beta_1 X_1 + e_1$ obtained results of the magnitude of the contribution of Supervision of supervisors independent variables to the dependent variable of principal's motivation of $0.015 \times 100\% = 1.5\%$. ANOVA value of $F = 2.557$, $p = 0.016 < 0.05$ that the regression model can be used to predict the values of Supervision of supervisors variables. Regression Standardized Residual Histogram means that the first structural regression equation $X_2 = \beta_1 X_1 + e_1$ residual data shows the normal data trend. The P-P Normal Diagram the Plot of Regression Standardized Residual data spreads in a straight line so that the residual data is concluded to meet the assumption of normality. The Scatterplot of Regression Standardized Residual Diagram illustrates the absence of certain patterns because the irregular spread points above and below the 0 axis on the Y axis, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity. In the coefficient column value- $t = 2.427$ with $p = 0.016$ ($0.016 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected meaning H_1 is accepted. So that it can be concluded that Supervision of supervisors influences the Principal's Motivation.

Based on the results of the multiple regression test the second structural equation is obtained $Y = \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_1 + e_2$. The amount of the Supervision of supervisors contribution and the Principal's Motivation variable together with the Teachers Performance variable is $0.592 \times 100\% = 59.2\%$. Durbin-Watson (DW) = 1.739, there are $1.65 < DW < 2.35$ so there is no autocorrelation in the regression model (Tihendradi, 2005). ANOVA, $F = 5.334$, $p = 0.006 < 0.05$ means that the regression model $Y = \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_1 + e_2$ is a good regression model. VIF = 1,015 fairly high correlation between independent variables, but < 10 means there is no multicollinearity. The Regression Standardized Residual Histogram means that the residual data equation $Y = \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_1 + e_2$ shows the normal data trend where the Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual shows the data spread in a straight line. Scatterplot of Regression Standardized Residual shows that there are no specific patterns because the irregular spread points above and below the 0 axis on the Y axis can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity. The results of the coefficient concluded that Supervision of supervisors and Principal's Motivation had an effect on each teacher's performance with $p = 0.000$ and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$.

The third structural equation $Z = \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_5 Y + \beta_3 X_1 + e_3$ shows the magnitude of the contribution of Supervision of supervisors variables, Principal's Motivation variables, and Teacher Performance variables are equal to the Quality variable of $0.423 \times 100\% = 42.3\%$. Durbin-Watson (DW) = 1.917 in the range of $1.65 < DW < 2.35$ concluded that there is no autocorrelation in the regression model. ANOVA, $F = 6.082$ and $p = 0.001 < 0.05$ means that the regression model is a good regression model $Z = \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_5 Y + \beta_3 X_1 + e_3$ that can be used to predict the value of the research data. Coefficients Motivation Head tolerance values 0.945 and VIF = 1.058, Teacher tolerance performance 0.927 and VIF = 1,078, and Supervision of supervisors tolerance value 0.960 and VIF = 1.042 shows there is a fairly high and strong correlation between fellow independent variables. For the three variables, the free VIF value is 1,058 and 1,078 and 1,042, the

value is <10 , so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity. The Residual Regression Standardized Histogram Diagram that the residual data equation shows the normal data trend. In the Normal P-P diagram, the Plot of Regression Standardized Residual shows that the data spreads on a straight line can be concluded that the residual data meets the assumption of normality. Scatterplot of Regression Standardized Residual Diagram does not occur in certain patterns because the irregular spread points above and below the 0 axis on Y axis concluded there are no heteroscedasticity symptoms in the regression model $Z = \beta_2X_2 + \beta_5Y + \beta_3X_1 + e_3$ Given the required assumptions have been fulfilled the regression model $Z = \beta_2X_2 + \beta_5Y + \beta_3X_1 + e_3$ is said to be a good model and feasible to use in answering research hypotheses with a summary table of the following equations:

Table 2: Summary of Third Structural Equations

Third Structural Equations			
Supervision of Supervisors, Principals Motivation, Teacher Performance, Quality of Kindergarten			
Variable	β	T	p
Principals Motivation	.104	1.147	.023
Teacher Performance	.654	5.006	.000
Academic Supervisor Supervision	.103	1.080	.025

In the coefficient column concluded Supervision of Supervisors, Principals Motivation, Teacher Performance affect the Quality with each value $p = 0.023$, $p = 0.000$, $p = 0.025 < p = 0.05$.

Table 3: Summary of Direct Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Relationship Coefficient (B)	P	Decision
Ho1: Supervision of Supervisors has no effect on Principals Motivation	0.121	.016	Rejected
Ho2: Principals Motivation has no effect on teacher performance	0.657	.000	Rejected
Ho3: Supervision of Supervisors has no effect on teacher performance	0.788	.000	Rejected
Ho4: Principals Motivation has no effect on quality	0.104	.023	Rejected
Ho5: Supervision of Supervisors has no effect on quality	0.654	.000	Rejected
Ho6: Teacher performance has no effect on quality	0.103	.025	Rejected

Direct Hypothesis Decision Results for Ho₁, Ho₂, Ho₃, Ho₄, Ho₅, Ho₆ all are rejected, meaning Hi₁, Hi₂, Hi₃, Hi₄, Hi₅, Hi₆ all of the results of Hi research are accepted.

Table 4: Decision of Indirect Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Relationship Coefficient (Beta)		Decision
	Direct	Indirect	
Ho ₇ : Teacher performance is not an intermediary between the Principal's Motivation and the Quality of Kindergarten	0.104	$0.656 \times 0.654 = 0,429$	Rejected
Ho ₈ : Teacher performance is not an intermediary relationship between Supervision of Supervisors and Quality of Kindergarten	0.103	$0.743 \times 0.654 = 0,486$	Rejected
Ho ₉ : Principal's Motivation is not an intermediary relationship between Supervision of Supervisors and Quality of Kindergarten	0.103	$0.121 \times 0.104 = 0,013$	Not Rejected
Ho ₁₀ : Principal's Motivation and Teacher Performance is not an intermediary between the Supervision of Supervisors and the Quality of Kindergarten	0.103	$0.121 \times 0.656 \times 0.654 = 0,059$	Not Rejected

The results of the Indirect Hypothesis Decision for Ho₇ and Ho₈ were rejected, meaning Hi₇ and Hi₈ both of the results of Hi research were accepted. While the Results of the Indirect Hypothesis Decision for Ho₉ and Ho₁₀ were accepted, meaning Hi₉ and Hi₁₀ both of the results of Hi research were rejected. Based on the results of the research, multiple regression tests for each structural equation obtained a new path model as shown below:

Figure 2: New Path Model Structural Relationship between X1, X2, Y, and Z

Mean score statistics achieved from the results of each variable Principal's Motivation 69.1%, Supervision of Supervisors 68.3%, Teacher Performance 71.9% and Quality 60.4% all in the medium category, according to three interval groups namely low group (less than [mean - 1 standard deviation]), moderate group (mean - 1 standard deviation mean + 1 standard deviation), and high group (more than [mean + 1 standard deviation]). The results of testing the research hypothesis are:

- 1) Hypothesis 1: There is a direct contribution from Supervision of Supervisors to Principal's Motivation. Agree with Arikunto (2008) defines that supervision is assistance in order to develop teaching and learning situations in order to get better conditions. In line with the research conducted by Andarwati (2015), Nurmalina (2017), Latiana et al. (2018) and M.C.M Ehren et al. (2015).
- 2) Hypothesis 2: There is a direct contribution of the Principal's Motivation to Teacher performance, confirmed by Hardiana (2013), that the teacher's performance will be good if there are stimulus that generate motivation, both inside and outside motivation. Motivation will lead to positive things if it affects the satisfaction of the teacher and vice versa, if it leads to negative things, it will have an effect on dissatisfaction. The results of this study are in line with the research of Suwedana et al. (2013), Agustina et al. (2016), Subawa et al. (2015), Kusumayani et al. (2013), Wihartuti et al. (2016), and Kongnyuy (2015).
- 3) Hypothesis 3: There is a direct contribution of Supervision of Supervisors to Teacher's performance. The result with Melvin's theory is that the purpose of supervision is to build teacher competency, it requires interaction and a clear role between superiors and teachers in order to achieve the objectives of supervision. In line with the research of Nurmalina (2017), Subawa et al. (2015), Coimbra (2013), Eya and Chukwu (2012), Ikegbusi (2016), Modebelu (2008), Walker (2016), and Ughamadu (2015).
- 4) Hypothesis 4: There is a direct contribution of the Principal's Motivation to quality, then. Based on Barelson and Steiner the theory that motivation as an impulse, activating or moving, and which directs or channels behavior towards the goal. In line with Rahayu (2015), Kusumawati et al. (2017), Larasati (2010), Owala (2016), and Akyem (2010).
- 5) Hypothesis 5: There is a direct contribution from Supervision of Supervisors to quality. Dharma's theory that effective supervision is an important factor to increase work productivity, so that it can improve the quality of schools (Dharma, 2001). In line with the research of Andarwati's (2015), Kusumawati et al. (2017), Tandika (2015), and Ehren et al. (2015).
- 6) Hypothesis 6: There is a direct contribution of Teacher Performance to quality. Theory of Sagala (2008), in the book Professional Ability of teachers and Education Personnel, that qualified teachers are undoubtedly capable of carrying out effective and efficient education, teaching and training. Same with the research of Larasati (2010), Rahayu (2015), Agustina et al. (2016), Brayfiled and Walter (2004).
- 7) Hypothesis 7: There is a Principal's Motivation contribution through intermediary Teacher Performance to quality. Wirakartakusumah theory (Rajagukguk, 2009) in order to achieve quality education, a new paradigm in education is needed that focuses on accountability, autonomy, accreditation and evaluation. The principal who provides motivation and advice to the teacher when getting a problem during the learning process so that the teacher improves

the quality of teaching which also improves the quality of the school. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Larasati (2010), Juweni (2016), Rahayu (2015), Ikegbusi (2016), Eya and Chukwu (2012), Okobia (2015), Ofojebe (2007), Jonesboro (2013), and Olatoye (2006).

- 8) Hypothesis 8: There is a Supervision of Supervisors contribution through intermediaries Teacher performance on quality. The theory of Aedi (2014: 356) says there are four strategies to improve teacher professionalism through supervision. One of them is the need for teachers to be involved individually or in groups in supervision activities carried out by supervisors and principals. In line with the research of Sudarmi (2016), Andarwati (2015), Latiana et al. (2018), and Ehren et al. (2015).
- 9) Hypothesis 9: There is no Supervision of Supervisors contribution through intermediary Principal's Motivation on quality. Conventional Supervision Model Theory (Traditional), where this model has the characteristics of a leader who is corrective and is looking for mistakes. According to Olivia (1984), the behavior is called Snooper Vision (spying) or also referred to as corrective supervision. The results of this study indirectly supervised supervisors through intermediary principal's motivation there was no influence on quality. Besides that it can be caused because if Supervisory Supervision is not good, even though the principal's motivation is good, this does not affect quality improvement. In practice, finding fault and suppressing these subordinates is still widely practiced in this life. The supervisors came to school and asked the name of the unit of study, saying that this was wrong and should be like this. Supervision practices like this are conventional supervision methods. Principal when reprimanded by supervisors always accept, they are reluctant to argue or express opinions. This does not mean that supervisors may not show errors. The problem is how the supervisor informs him that he must correct the error. Principals will be happy to accept and see that something must be improved. The method used must be tactically pedagogical or by using other words, using the acceptance language instead of using the language of rejection (Gordon, 1988). It could also be done by carrying out a Scientific Supervision Model, where scientific supervision has several characteristics including: (1) Continuously implemented and planned. (2). Use certain and systematic procedures and techniques. (3) Using data collection instruments. (4). Having objective data obtained from real errors.
- 10) Hypothesis 10: There is no contribution between Supervision of Supervisors and Quality through intermediary Principal's Motivation and Teacher Performance. The results of this study indirectly supervised supervisors through intermediary motivation of the head and the teacher's performance had no influence on quality. The connection is with good supervisory supervision but the principal is not able to motivate the teacher so that as a team does not succeed in achieving school goals and does not affect quality. Conversely, if Supervision of

Supervisors is not good, even though the Kindergarten Principal's Motivation and Teacher Performance has been done well, this does not affect the quality improvement of Kindergarten in West Banjarmasin District. This is in line with the research of Balci et al. (2011) which states that teachers and supervisors are like two opposing camps: teachers describe supervisors as people who punish teachers, create mistakes that cause stress, try to change and change teachers, make teachers feel depressed and ill, and scare teachers during interrogation.

5. Suggestion

Research results: There are direct contributions: 1. Supervision of the supervisor to Kindergarten Principal's Motivation; 2. Principal's Motivation towards Teacher's performance; 3. Supervision of Supervisors on Teacher's performance; 4. Principal's Motivation towards quality; 5. Supervision of the supervisor on quality; 6. Teacher's performance on quality. There are indirect contributions: 7. Motivation through intermediaries Teacher performance on quality; 8. Supervision of Supervisors through intermediaries Teacher performance on quality. There are no contribution: 9. Supervision of the supervisor through intermediary of Principal's Motivation on quality; 10. Supervision of Supervisors and quality through intermediaries of Principal's Motivation and Teachers Performance in Kindergarten Sub District of West Banjarmasin.

Recommendations based on the results of this study are:

1. The implication of the results of this study on the development in order to achieve quality, the supervisor must carry out good supervision by fostering the Principal to implement good Principal motivation, which will make the teacher perform well, thus improving the quality of the school.
2. It is recommended to the Ministry of Education and the Central Team in particular the Head of the Education and Culture Office of South Kalimantan Province to make more frequent training and training programs and improve competencies for Supervisors, Principals and Teachers in Banjarmasin City. This is suggested because the results of this study indicate that if the principal's motivation is good then it will influence the teacher's performance.
3. For Supervisors it is hoped that they will continue to continuously implement supervision and guidance to the principal and teacher.
4. For the Principal of Kindergarten, in running management, a supervisory system for improving Kindergarten management, motivating, directing, and coordinating teachers in order to improve teacher performance and quality of Kindergarten.
5. For Teachers to increase knowledge and insight in planning, implementing and evaluating in the process of teaching and learning activities.
6. To other researchers, the results of this study still have limitations and weaknesses because it needs to be continued with similar research and the

results of this study can be used as input material. This research is still taking data through the teacher about motivation. It is better if this research is explored based on the principal's self, that is, for example the motivation test or motivation test is replaced with other variables.

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